

E-Commerce Fraud Detection Tools

Dr. N.A. Padmalatha

*Assistant Professor, School of Commerce and Management Studies
Dayananda Sagar University, Shavige Malleshwara Hills
Kumaraswamy Layout, Bangalore*

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2020

P-ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Padmalatha, NA.

“E-Commerce Fraud
Detection Tools.”

*Shanlax International
Journal of Management*,
vol. 7, no. S1, 2020,
pp. 24–32.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3737716](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3737716)

Abstract

India is a cash based society. However, as per the reports of NASSCOM, India is expected to have Internet users base of about 730 million by the end of 2020. It has been noted that by 2020, Indian e-commerce industry is expected to reach \$34 billion, with 200 million individuals transacting online, growing 3X over 2015. This spread of e-Commerce has led to the rise of several niche players who largely specialize their products around a specific theme including fraud detection tools. Experts predict online credit card fraud to increase to \$32 billion by 2020. In order to combat technology, it is absolute necessary to combat fraud effectively. Technological advancements in data analytics such as link analysis, data visualization, predictive modelling and other analytic testing are usual tests to identify the online fraud.

Current fraud detection techniques, however, are far from accurate, can result in significant financial losses, inconvenience and dissatisfaction to customers. In this article an attempt has been made to find the technologies to address the fraud and steps of adopting the fraud detection and prevention technology. The objectives of the research paper are to find types of e-Commerce frauds and to develop the mechanism(process) and technologies used in detection and prevention of frauds in consumer transaction. Fraud detection methods can be deployed either through IT solution or through integrated Business and IT solution. Through effective fraud detection methods, particularly with the use of technologies, losses can be reduced effectively.

Today, a number of companies wanting to incorporate proactive fraud risk management at various stages in identification of frauds, identification of fraudster's relatives, collecting evidence and interpretation. Hence the major outcome of the study is to assess the fraud prevention technologies and suggest possibilities of adoption of the technologies.

Keywords: Fraud detection Technology, Online business, Ecommerce.

Introduction

India is a cash-based society. Cash on delivery is the most preferred payment method. As per the reports of “The Future of Internet in India”, by 2020, 50% of travel transactions to be online and 70% of e-Commerce transactions via mobile phones. By 2020 (NASSCOM Report), the number of online shoppers is likely to cross 175 million. Demand for International consumer products will be growing faster than in-country supply from authorized distributors and e-commerce offerings.

Fraud can be committed by employee acting alone, or in collusion with another party (a second employee) or a third party. Because of the availability information any person can collate the information about the company, its employees and clients in a damaging manner. A recent study by KPMG based on India Fraud survey 2012, indicated that with the ever-increasing use of technology in every business, is inadvertently leading to more sophisticated and complete frauds than before.

As per the Reports of Wikipedia, India has an Internet users base of about 475 million as of July, 2019. This number has crossed 627 million by the end of 2019. The spread of e-Commerce has led to the rise of several niche players who largely specialize their products around a specific theme. Largest e-Commerce Companies in India are Flipkart, Amazon, Myntra, Paytm, and Snapdeal. Payment options for online shopping in India includes billing to mobile phones and landlines, cash on delivery, cheque, debit card, direct debit in some countries, electronic money, gift cards, wire Transfer/ Delivery on Payment, etc.

As per TechARC's report, ecommerce contributed to 51% of total ad fraud in India through customer acquisition, engagement and retention Current fraud detection techniques, however, are far from accurate, and can resulting significant financial loses, inconvenience and dissatisfaction to customers. Reports about online frauds in India, about Indian Railways(2018, November), Indian Railways deactivated 1,268 user IDs on IRCTC after forfeiting 1,875 scheduled e-tickets after it conducted raids against e-ticketing fraud in over 100 cities in the country. 1,875 scheduled e-tickets worth Rs 35 lakh were forfeited. On 2018, July 37 people were allegedly duped on OLX by fraudsters who used leaked soft copies of Aadhaar and ID cards of CISF and Army Personnel . This resulted in CISF and Army Personnel received several calls and complaint emails- questioning the integrity of the men in uniform.

With the effective use of Fraud detection technologies, losses can be reduced effectively. Today, a number of companies wanting to incorporate proactive fraud risk management in their companies at various stages in identification of fraud, identification of fraudster's relatives and close friends, collect evidence and interpretation.

Fraud Detection Technology Across Various Stages

1. **Identification of fraud:** Data across different period of time need to be analysed for identifying anomalies. However, new suppliers or new customer involved with the suspicious transactions may not be in the master data of the organization. Data analytics tools like SAP, Case Ware IDEA, etc. can be used to identify the anomalies.
2. **Identification of fraudster's relatives and close friends:** The mobile phones and social networking applications such as Facebook, Twitter, WeChat, Instagram , WhatsApp provides an opportunity to observe interests, linking, lifestyle , characteristics etc. Social networking analysis tools, such as NodeXL, SVAT, Gephi, etc. could be deployed to achieve the same goal. Communication records can also be used to identify the reasons behind the crime.
3. **Collect Evidence:** In a digital world, most all data are stored in cell phones, Servers, cloud systems. Forensic tools such as Encase or Helix can be the technological solutions for the same.
4. **Interpretation:** In order to represent the trends tools such as Qlik, or tableau can be deployed.

Features of Fraud Detection Tools

In order to combat frauds, new and up-to-date technology is absolutely necessary . It involves procedures to collect data, quick evaluation of the collected data, identifying activities, formulating patterns of fraudulent activities. Risk assessment analyses must also be performed to identify where the weak links are.

Fraud Detection Tools in the Industry are

- Software for continuous monitoring of business transactions
- IT based tools for retrospective identification of fraudulent payments or other abusive activity
- Software for continuous monitoring of business communications
- IT based tools for identification of unethical behaviour based on social network analysis.

Technological advancements in data analytics such as link analysis, data visualization, predictive modelling and other analytic testing are usual tests to identify the anomalies.

Pattern of Fraud as given by Association of certified Fraud examiner's Reports(ACEF), are

1. Employee generated :This can be solved by background checks on employees when hiring, restrictions on employee activities, awareness in the organization
2. Organization Generated: This can be prevented by having polices and procedures for using the organization's funds, Safeguarding assets and documents, promoting appropriate workflow
3. Third Party generated: This can be prevented by safeguarding organization's data access, risk assessment techniques

Adoption of Integrated Technology in Fraud Detection

Data scientists can solve fraud problem using machine learning and predictive analytics. It uses various algorithms to facilitate the machines to respond to different situations for which they have not been programmed explicitly. Advanced machine learning tools can automatically update its models to reflect the trends. With increased data set, machine learning models can pick similarities and differences between multiple behaviours. The advantages of machines for the fraud detection are speed, scale and efficiency.

The stages for fraud detection involves

- a. Getting historical data
- b. Building models for predicting fraud
- c. Using the model for prediction.

However, the machine learning requires significant number of cases or large datasets to give an accurate judgement. Other challenges in this approach are high infrastructural costs, strict regulations and risk of replacing existing technology.

Current Scenario

As per the RBI reports, of more than 1.1 million people who reported fraud, 21% had lost more than \$63 million dollar from 2016. According to RBI data, of the total 53,334 cases of frauds during 2008-09 and 2018-19 fiscal years, involving Rs 2.05 lakh crore, a highest of 6,811 were reported by ICICI bank involving Rs 5,033.8 crore.

As per Tech ARC's report titled "India digital ad-fraud market" states that in 2018, ad fraud cost a total of \$1.63 billion, contributing to 8.7% of the global fraud. The report states that Ecommerce contributed to over 51% of the total ad fraud in India, via customer acquisition, engagement and retention.

Web platforms were more susceptible to frauds over app fraud because their digital teams were more likely to look at app fraud over web fraud. The web had higher chances of fake leads and keyword abuse over apps. Despite this, app fraud led to 85% of total digital ad fraud. Some of the interesting acts are:

- Video fraud is becoming more sophisticated to gain more on premium advertising channels as video consumption increases

- Both traditional and online marketers need to look at O2O (unclear if online to offline or otherwise) for ad fraud strategy.
- Companies with solutions for ad fraud are ‘better equipped’ to have higher user engagement because they can contain abuse

The top few fraud risks that have the potential to pose threats to businesses in India are the following: Data or information threat and IP infringement; Bribery and corruption; Fraud penetrated by Senior Management; Fraudulent disbursements (e.g. billing schemes, payroll schemes, expense disbursement schemes, check tampering); Vendor fraud or kickbacks; Regulatory non-compliance; Theft or misuse of inventory; Misappropriation of assets (e.g. theft of cash or receipts)

Literature Review

The article (Parr et al), mentions about the different aspects such as ways in which small business owners can combat the theft, ways of identifying weak links, types of controls, types of restriction of activities. Even though author mentions that availability of tools for the specific requirement of business, the exact tools were not discussed. Machine learning as an important tool for solving business fraud is widely adopted. Automated fraud detection system is highly successful in solving the problem. Stages of machine learning and Models used were discussed in the article. (How machine learning facilitates fraud detection, 2019). The article (Detecting financial fraud using machine learning, 2018) discusses about how to handle imbalanced data in machine learning. Depending on the data, the author has mentioned the use of techniques such as SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique), Random Under Sampler or SMOTE+ENN (Edited Nearest Neighbour) technique. In the article Millar (2010),

Peter Millar (2010, August 16), “7 steps to jump start your anti-fraud program” mentions about the steps which are worth noting: Building profile of potential frauds; Test transactional data for possible indicators of fraud; Improve controls by implementing continuous auditing and monitoring; Communicate the monitoring activity throughout the organization; Provide management with immediate notification when things are going wrong; Fix any broken controls immediately; Expand the scope and repeat.

Objectives of the Research are

1. To study and find types of e-commerce frauds
2. To develop the mechanism (process) and technologies used in detection and prevention of frauds in consumer transaction
3. To assess the technologies trend and suggest possibilities of adoption

Research Finding

Some of the interesting observations related to ecommerce fraud in online industry are:

- Young Professionals are potential fraudsters
- Small businesses with fewer than 100 employees are most susceptible to occupational fraud.
- Internet fraud is usually penetrated by employees
- Over 90% of online fraud detection platforms use transaction rules to detect suspicious transactions.

Popular Types of Ecommerce Frauds are

- **Identity theft:** Most common type of ecommerce fraud causing concern. Fraudster targets personal information such as name, addresses, e-mail addresses, credit card or account information.

- **Friendly Fraud:** Customers order goods or services and pay for them – preferably using a “pull” payment method like a credit card or direct debit. Then, however, they deliberately initiate a charge-back, claiming that their credit card or account details were stolen. They are reimbursed – but they keep the goods or services.
- **Clean Fraud:** A stolen credit card is used to make the purchase, but the transaction is then manipulated, in such a way that fraud detection function are circumvented.
- **Affiliate Fraud:** Affiliate process can be done either using a fully automated process or by getting real people to get into merchant’s sites using fake accounts. This can be done by the fraudster by manipulating traffic or signup statistics.
- **Triangulation Fraud:** In this case, fraud is carried out via three ways. First, fraudster will have a fake online storefront, which offers high demand products at different process especially at extremely low prices. The user gives data related to credit card, and addresses, which is the main motive of the falsified storefront. Using the stolen credit card data and name collected, goods are collected and shipped to the original customer. The final point in the fraud triangle is making additional purchases using the stolen credit cards. Because of the unknown connect between order data and credit card numbers, it is almost impossible to connect. As a result, the fraud remains undiscovered for a longer period of time, resulting in greater damages.
- **Merchant fraud:** Merchant fraud is another method which must be mentioned. It’s very simple: goods are offered at cheap prices, but are never shipped. The payments are, of course, kept. This method of fraud also exists in wholesale. It is not specific to any particular payment method, but this is, of course, where no-chargeback payment methods (most of the push payment types) come into their own.

The Various Frauds Identified at Various Stages of Ecommerce Marketplace are **Order Placement Processing**

- Inflated MRP for the discounts
- Unauthorized price change
- Unauthorised/fake orders
- Presence of black listed entities in the system (who tend to re-apply under a new name to register in the system) in the absence of adequate vendor due diligence

Payment

- Credit/Debit Card fraud using stolen information
- Payment gateway vulnerabilities (Hacking, Lack of authenticated credentials etc.)
- Cash on delivery (non-receipt of payment, fraud by cash collection agent)

System/Network Operations

- Phishing fraud (Identity theft)
- Intrusion/Cyber attacks (e.g. malware)
- Pharming
- System manipulation e.g. redemption of coupon even on cancellation of order, avail discount on expired coupons, order executed without payment)

Returns and Refunds

- Counterfeit product returns
- Return of used products
- Tampering with product in order to return it
- Customer initiates chargeback without returning the product

To Develop the Mechanism (Process) and Technologies used in Detection and Prevention of Frauds in Consumer Transaction

Since the cost of trying to prevent fraud is far less expensive to business than the cost of fraud committed to business. The mechanism to prevent detection can be viewed as IT problem or a combination of IT problem and business problem.

A full and detailed examination can now be achieved via data analysis. Additionally, technology could be integrated into the fraud investigation process.

- **Building background information:** Once fraud is discovered, the first step was to build a basic background information understanding. In this aspect, it is necessary to comprehend a fraudster's relatives and close friends to establish his or her interpersonal relationships, then try to clarify the accomplice network. The prevalence of mobile phones and social networking apps such as Facebook, Twitter, WeChat, Instagram and WhatsApp provides investigators with a great opportunity to observe fraudsters' interests, lifestyle and characteristics. In addition, social networking analysis tools, like NodeXL, SVAT, Gephi, etc., could be deployed to achieve the same goal.
- **Finding fraudster's motives for crime:** Social networking analysis tools and communication records could be adapted to accomplish this aim. Patterns of illicit behaviour also need to be grappled with. In this aspect, it is useful to compare different data across different periods to identify anomalies. For instance, the fact that new suppliers involved with the suspicious transactions are never presented in the company's client master data is a warning sign. Evidence of specific or unprecedented accounting subjects, such as temporary payments or account receivables factoring, are also red flags. Those anomalies could be identified via several data analysis tools like SAP, CaseWare IDEA, etc.
- **Collecting Evidence:** In a digital world, almost all data is stored on electronic devices, such as cellphones, computers, servers, cloud systems, etc. Thus, it is vital to gather digital evidence through proper devices to prevent them from being polluted, which might result in them being unable to be presented in court. In this regard, forensic tools such as Encase, FTK or Helix are certified and commonly employed by investigators.
- **Interpreting the information:** Lastly, it is requisite to summarise all the information and make an interpretation – a task which is traditionally completed by investigators. With the development of computer technology, some programmes, such as Qlik or Tableau, could be applied to comprehensively display trends and variables, so that the whole story can be seen.

Even though advanced technology serves as great tool to combat fraud, the issue should be viewed as a combination of IT problem and business problem. The steps:

- Put a clear focus on segregation of duties (Spread and rotate financial responsibilities and financial control)
- Offer internal and external audits (monthly profit and loss reviews, monthly balance sheet reviews)
- Develop protocols for electronic banking transactions (e.g., limiting access, verbally confirming requests, two-step authentication process, safeguard data)

To Find the Technologies Trend and Suggest Possibilities of Adoption

Thanks to the evolution of technology, investigators can now conduct a thorough and complete audit of entire populations of transactions in a relatively short period.

- High performance computing redefines the possible: Today's high-performance analytics can rapidly analyze massive amounts of data using technologies such as grid computing, in-database analytics and in-memory analytics. Fraud analysts can now rapidly test multiple methods to

determine which models work best. Speedier model development/testing means better models get deployed sooner, giving institutions more agile response to the flash fraud and zero-day threats that can manifest in online channels. Hadoop brings high-performance data storage and processing to the fraud-fighting arsenal, operating on large clusters of commodity hardware. Hadoop makes it fast and affordable to support analytics processes that can find anomalies in millions of records. Analytical insights can be delivered to visual interfaces and automated workflow systems. Imagine arming your investigative team with visualizations that clarify where to look, along with supporting detail about threats as they are developing, rather than days or weeks later.

- Hybrid analytical techniques deliver richer insights: By combining analytical approaches, you can detect and prevent more fraud with fewer false positives, protecting the firm while preserving the quality of the customer experience. For example:
 - Hybrid models can use your firm's data at the core, consolidating data both internally and externally with a consortium model to create an even more predictive model.
 - The systems can detect variances that could indicate identity theft or malware.
 - Neural network models use machine learning to interactively learn from the data without human intervention, so the algorithms become smarter and more accurate with every iteration.
- Behavioral analytics transcend rules-based systems: Fraudsters can easily out-manoeuvre rules-based systems, so it's essential to have adaptive analytics that can detect unknown risks and new ways of trying to break the bank.
- A behavioral analytics approach captures behavioral patterns from every source and evaluates that information every time a transaction is scored. This process builds a deep profile of the historical norm for an account, card holder, customer, merchant, POS terminal, device, web session, etc. The more profiles available, the richer the understanding of whether a payment transaction or new product application is legitimate. The end goal for behavioral analytics will be to identify potentially fraudulent behavior before a payment is made or a customer's account is compromised.
- Investigative workflow becomes more efficient: Firms need to become more efficient in detecting, triaging and building investigations on suspicious activity. Four important must-haves make this possible. The ideal fraud solution would:
 - Stage the data so transactions can be bridged to associated accounts and those accounts to parties – and if applicable, to households, corporate parents or other networked entities.
 - Aggregate work items for a subject, rather than require analysts to review separate work items. This reduces the number of widgets to be worked and gives analysts a more complete view of subject behavior.
 - Present the most meaningful information. Why are there events on this subject? Who are the players in these transactions? What is normal for them? Does this merit further investigation?
 - Automatically assemble alerts from multiple monitoring systems, prioritize higher-risk activities and auto-assign alerts to investigators based on the firm's unique rules and requirements.

A well-designed fraud solution will reduce queries to source systems, increase efficiency and provide governance through automated workflow for dual controls for investigation and filing of regulatory reports.

- Financial institutions become crime-fighting partners: Leading institutions are establishing proactive intelligence units that scour negative news events, referrals, case data, social media, consortium data and cyber events to detect previously unknown risks. They are deploying in-memory data architectures that enable sophisticated analyses such as global search, text

mining, visualization, and network analysis to piece together clues from masses of disparate data. When attacks occur, or when helping law enforcement work critical events, firms now have the tools to provide immediate answers.

Suggestions

Ecommerce frauds are becoming sophisticated and customers are consistently challenged by the sophistication of frauds. Degree of sophistication tends to be sectoral in nature. It has been found by the researchers that IT, ITES and Financial services are more vulnerable to technology. Hence, Understanding the modulus operandi of the frauds and suggesting is not easy. Some of the suggestions are:

- **Stronger authentication:** Given the millennial generation's demand for convenience and frictionless commerce, the biggest challenge will be authenticating users without impeding the customer journey. Innovative fraud operations will find ways to tighten controls without inconveniencing users, perhaps through some combination of biometrics, near field communications and analytics.
- **More data for richer profiles:** Models and signatures will incorporate more data, such as from biometrics, consortia, interface devices, digital voice recordings and other novel sources. Information sharing among merchants and institutions will become more prevalent and efficient. We will continue to see convergence of cyber data with behavioral profiles for enhanced fraud detection.
- **High-performance fraud solutions:** Real-time prevention will be faster and scale to higher transaction throughput. More firms will implement fraud solutions that can correlate billions of daily transactions and enrich that data with business context and threat insights across the enterprise. In so doing, they will create smarter data that can be analyzed in many different combinations and peer groups – across products and organizational entities – to find anomalous behavior that could look innocuous in local context.
- **Usage of Integrated packages:** Expert System package FCI (Financial Crime Investigator), a package by Anthem Corporation, helps to identify fraud detection in purchase or in contracts. The user can write the query for fraud indication and then match the indicators to profiles of specific fraud schemes. The program generates detailed work plans, including further databases and on-line searches, designed to confirm or exclude each suspect scheme. These work plans also include information about what documents to review and what to look for, as well as who to interview and what to ask.

Conclusion

In modern business, transactions take place through a variety of payment channels such as credit /debit card, smartphones, kiosks, etc. At the same time fraudsters are becoming adept at finding weak links in the business transactions. Hence, detecting frauds is essential for any business. And, fraud detection is possible for banks and commercial industry with the advancement of technology. With the availability of increasing processing power, advancement in statistical modelling, ability to capture and store voluminous data organizations are adopting technology to detect fraud.

References

1. Arbind Singh, EY, "Changing face of fraud in India,
2. Cindy Parr, CFE, is a senior auditor with Whittaker Cooper Financial Group, Certified Public Accountants and Consultants.

3. Keith M(2015, Feb 25), “How technology is shaping the fight against fraud”, Inc.com , 22-Jan-2020.
4. Kuo Ming Huang(2017, February), Fraud Prevention and Detection- Focus on the technological trend, Financier Rafael Piere, January 17, 2018, Detecting financial fraud using machine learning: Winning the war against imbalanced data, Data Science
5. Stu Bradley, David Sewart(n.d.), “Five trends in fraud solution.”, SAS
6. (n.d.), How machine learning facilitates fraud detection, Maruthi Techlabs, Pvt Ltd., 2019.
7. Future of Internet in India, NASSCOM Report, 2020.
8. Indian Fraud Survey(2012), KPMG India Fraud Survey Report .